

INTRALAMINAR TOUGHENED CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES EXHIBITING SELF-HEALING CAPABILITIES

Thomas W. Loh, Raj B. Ladani, Everson Kandare

¹ Department of Aerospace Engineering and Aviation, School of Engineering, RMIT
University, Melbourne, VIC3001, Australia

Keywords: Braided composites, EMAA filaments, Fracture toughness, Self-healing

ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the interlaminar fracture toughness properties and the self-repair capability of carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy composite laminates incorporating intraply mendable thermoplastic filaments. A carbon fibre fabric was interlaced with mendable filaments of polyethylene-co-methacrylic acid (EMAA) via co-braiding. The EMAA-interlaced carbon fabric layers were stacked to create a pre-form which was subsequently thermo-formed and epoxy resin-infused to manufacture carbon-epoxy laminates. The effects of intraply-located EMAA filaments on the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness and self-healing efficiency of the carbon-epoxy composite were investigated. Results from this study showed that the presence of EMAA improved the interlaminar fracture toughness (both the crack initiation and steady-state crack growth resistance) of the carbon-epoxy composite and enabled healing of the delamination crack. The delamination crack growth resistance of healed-composites containing EMAA was found to be superior to that of the baseline composite (without EMAA).

1 INTRODUCTION

Because of the relatively weak interlaminar bonding, fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) composite laminates are vulnerable to impact-, thermal- and fatigue-induced delamination and matrix cracking, which can ultimately lead to catastrophic structural failure. FRP composite structures will inevitably experience loading conditions that can cause matrix damage, delamination crack initiation and subsequent crack propagation during their service life. To avert structural losses due to the initiation and resultant uninterrupted delamination crack growth, it is imperative that the composite design process incorporates technologies for improved interlaminar fracture toughness as well as cost-effective delamination damage repair. Interlaminar toughening of FRP composites is generally achieved via polymer matrix modification [1-6] and the integration of through-the-thickness reinforcements via stitching [7], tufting [8, 9] and z-pinning [10]. While effective in resisting the initiation and growth of short delamination cracks (typically smaller than 2 mm), matrix modification is generally not as effective as through-the-thickness reinforcements in resisting the propagation of longer delamination cracks. To achieve enhanced crack initiation and crack growth resistance, researchers have taken advantage of the diverse toughening mechanisms exhibited by multiscale toughening agents – from the nano- to the macro-scale. [11-13]. Ravindran and others showed that the inclusion of carbon nanofibers [11-13] and graphene nanoplatelets [13] were effective in resisting the growth of short delamination cracks. At the macro-scale, z-pinning has emerged as an effective and simpler method of enhancing the delamination resistance, impact damage tolerance and the laminate joint strength [10].

Despite the significant improvements in the intrinsic interlaminar fracture toughness, the critical challenge for toughened composites is their reparability. The delaminated composite must be replaced or restored to its original service condition via mechanically-fastened or adhesively-bonded (i.e. scarf) repairs [14]. Mechanically-fastened repairs are generally unacceptable on physically-thin laminates due to the introduction of stress concentrations around the fasteners. While preferred over mechanically-fastened repairs, the complexity, relatively high costs and limited durability of

adhesively-bonded repairs are some of the major hurdles with this technology. For example, scarf repairs involve extensive surface preparation, which is both costly and may also expose repair teams to occupational hazards, including the inhalation of fine dust particles and possibly nanomaterials. Also, the fractured through-the-thickness reinforcements (i.e. z-pins, fibre tows, carbon-based fillers) cannot be repaired and will, therefore, be of no benefit in the repaired composite. In response to these challenges, self-healing composite technologies [15-20] that require non-invasive interventions in restoring the composite structural integrity following delamination crack damage, have increasingly attracted interest from researchers in this field. Some of the self-repairing methods can be used repeatedly as some healing agents are preserved during the repair process. Thermoplastic particulates can be added to the thermosetting resin matrices during composite fabrication to act as healing agents in repairing delamination cracks when activated by heat [21]. However, the relatively high-volume fractions of healing agent required to achieve effective self-repair can lead to processing challenges such as “caking” and increased matrix viscosity, which may lead to increased composite porosity. An emerging alternative method which has attracted increased focus involves through-the-thickness stitching of FRP composite laminates using mendable polymers such as polyethylene-co-methacrylic acid (EMAA) [22-25]. Since the dry reinforcement fibre pre-forms can be stitched using standard stitching techniques before resin infusion, this method does not affect the resin flow during composite manufacture precluding the formation of internal defects such as voids and resin-rich pockets.

Yang and others [22, 23] recently demonstrated that through-the-thickness stitching of FRP laminate using EMAA resulted in a composite exhibiting high delamination resistance and possessing self-repair capability. Notwithstanding beneficial improvements in delamination resistance, impact damage tolerance, and the self-repair capability, interlaminar toughening via through-the-thickness stitching does adversely impact the composite in-plane mechanical properties. Pingkarawat and others [24] reported a 2% reduction in both the tensile and compression properties (elastic modulus and strength) for every 1% weight fraction increase in the healing agent, EMAA. The authors attributed the reduction in the mechanical properties of the stitched composite to the microstructural damage caused by the stitching process, especially fibre damage, fibre waviness and fibre crimping [10]. Pingkarawat and Mouritz [25] reported substantial reductions (up to 50% in some cases) in the tensile and compression properties with increasing stitch size and stitch density. The increase in stitch size and stitch density exacerbates fibre breakage during the stitching process, promotes the formation of resin-rich pockets near the stitches, reduces fibre content and enhances fibre waviness and fibre crimping. Since laminate damage affects both the interply and intraply regions, it is, therefore, essential to have the healing agent even distributed at the ply interface and within the ply [22]. To this end, a method enabling the placement of healing agents at both the interply and the intraply without substantial adverse impact on the in-plane mechanical property of FRP composites has been elusive.

The study presented in this paper, therefore, investigated a novel concept of integrating healing agents within the fabric ply to minimise fibre damage, fibre waviness and fibre crimping. Further, the presence of the healing agent at both the interply and intraply locations could serve to improve the interlaminar fracture toughness and enable self-repair capability without compromising the in-plane mechanical properties of the resultant composite. Co-braiding of the mendable thermoplastic (EMAA) filaments into carbon fabric provides a simple and practical means of potentially realising enhanced intrinsic interlaminar fracture toughness and the self-repair capability in FRP composites. In one case, the carbon fabric layers interlaced with EMAA filaments were thermo-formed at an elevated temperature (150°C) under an applied pressure (1 atm) to promote the partial melting and subsequent fusion of EMAA filaments located within adjacent plies. The interply fusion of self-healing EMAA filaments resulted in the creation of a 3D network which should enable the delivery of the healing agent to multiple interply and intraply damage sites during the healing operation. Furthermore, as evident from the stitched composite research [22-25], the fused interply EMAA ligaments do improve the interlaminar fracture toughness of FRP composites. This study explored the effects of an intraply-embedded healing agent, EMAA, on delamination toughness, and the healing efficiency of carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy composites providing mechanistic elucidation of the experimental observations.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials and composite manufacturing

Nucrel[®] 960 resin polymer, an ethylene acid copolymer containing 19% by weight of methacrylic acid randomly distributed along the co-polymer chain, EMAA, was supplied by Dupont, USA in the form of pellets. The EMAA pellets were extruded into 1.10 ± 0.02 mm-diameter filaments using the 3devo filament maker operating at 135°C (zone 1), 155°C (zone 2), 145°C (zone 3) and 135°C (zone 4) and a screw speed of 2.5 rpm. Never twisted carbon fibre tows (12K) of nominal density 1.79 g/cm³, tensile modulus 250 GPa and tensile strength 4,900 MPa were supplied by DowAksa, Turkey. The diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DEGBA) resin (SR8100)[®] and diamine hardener (SD8824)[®] epoxy system was supplied by Sicomin, France. The VTM-264[®] prepreg was supplied by Advanced Composites, UK while the epoxy-based adhesive, Araldite 420[®], was supplied by Huntsman, UK.

The carbon fibre tows and EMAA filaments were wound onto bobbins and loaded onto the 48-carrier Herzog[®] braiding machine. The braiding machine was operated at a production speed of 30 m/h and a horn speed of 38 rpm to achieve a regular (2-over, 2-under) triaxial braid fabric around a 50 mm-diameter mandrel. When present, the EMAA filaments were aligned along the axial (0°) direction evenly bisecting the 90° angle between the $\pm 45^\circ$ bias carbon fibre tows as shown in Fig. 1. The average spacing between adjacent axial EMAA filaments was ~ 6.25 mm resulting in an EMAA areal density of 125 g/m². The cylindrical braid sleeves were then cut open into 150 mm-wide planar fabrics for use in the composite manufacturing process.

Figure 1: A photographic image of a (2/2) triaxial carbon/EMAA braided fabric with axially-aligned EMAA filaments (translucent) bisecting the $\pm 45^\circ$ carbon fibre tow angles.

Four EMAA filament-interlaced braid fabrics were stacked in such a way that the EMAA filaments assumed the $[0/90]_s$ lay-up configuration. Two additional braided fabric plies (without EMAA filaments) were placed on either side of the four EMAA-interlaced plies to absorb excess EMAA that could leak during the thermo-forming process. Three composite batches were manufactured: (i) the laminate without EMAA, (ii) the virgin EMAA-incorporated laminate and (iii) the laminate incorporating thermo-formed EMAA filaments. For the third composite batch, thermo-forming was achieved by vacuum-bagging the EMAA-interlaced fabrics followed by thermal treatment at 150°C for 4 min. The thermo-forming process facilitated the flow of molten EMAA between adjacent plies resulting in a 3D intra- and inter-ply EMAA network. The vacuum bag resin infusion (VBRI) process operated at room temperature (23°C) was used to impregnate the fabric lay-up using the de-gassed 100:22 wt./wt. epoxy resin/hardener mixture. The resultant composite panel was cured under vacuum and ambient conditions for 24 h followed by post-curing at 60°C for 8 h in a conventional oven. The three carbon-epoxy composite batches being – the first without EMAA, the second containing virgin EMAA filaments and the third incorporating thermo-formed EMAA filaments are identified as the baseline, EMAA-0 and EMAA-4, respectively.

2.2 Evaluation of the interlaminar fracture toughness

The interlaminar fracture toughness of the carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy composite laminates (with and without EMAA) was evaluated using the double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens (Fig. 2) per the ASTM D5528 mode I Standard. The DCB specimens were 150 mm long and 25 mm wide. A 55 mm long and 30 μm -thick polymethylpentene (PMP) pre-crack film was inserted along the mid-plane at one end of the specimen during lay-up to initiate delamination. The DCB specimens were reinforced by 12-ply VTM-264 unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminates to prevent excessive bending and possible failure due to the enhanced interlaminar fracture toughness. The VTM-264 reinforcement laminates and the loading pins were bonded to the DCB specimens using Araldite 420[®]. After the initial DCB test, the EMAA-containing composites were healed via thermal exposure at 150°C for 30 min, (i.e., an initial 20 min without applied pressure followed by a further 10 min under pressure) according to an established procedure [26]. The interlaminar fracture toughness of the healed DCB specimens was re-evaluated to quantify the fracture toughness recovery relative to the pristine composite.

Figure 2: Schematic of the DCB composite specimen.

The fracture toughness was measured by monotonically-increasing the crack opening displacement (COD) at a rate of 1 mm/min with the crack growth monitored via a travelling microscope positioned along the length of the DCB specimen. The modified beam theory, as suggested by the ASTM D5528 mode I Standard, was used for calculating the interlaminar fracture toughness according to:

$$G_I = \frac{3P\delta}{2b(a + |\Delta|)} \quad (1)$$

where P and δ are the applied load and the loading point displacement, respectively. The variables, a , b and Δ represent the delamination length, the DCB specimen width and the adjusted delamination length correction factor accounting for possible rotation at the delamination front, respectively.

2.3 Microstructural analysis of the DCB specimens

The microstructure of the composite laminates was characterised before and after the fracture toughness evaluation via X-ray computed tomography (CT) using a General Electric Phoenix v|tome|xS instrument fitted with a micro-tube. The microstructural analysis was also conducted following self-repair of the delamination. The scans were performed at 60 kV and 350 μA with a voxel size of 25.8 μm . Up to 2000 image projections were collected and merged to generate the 3D volumetric representation of the DCB specimen from which 2D-sectional images were extracted. The volume fractions of the EMAA filaments were determined via the X-ray computed tomography using the VolMaxStudio 3.0 Program. The carbon fibre volume fractions were determined via the conventional ASTM D3171 standard for determining composite constituent volume fractions.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructural analysis of the pristine composite laminates

The carbon fibre volume fractions in the baseline, EMAA-0 and EMAA-4 composite laminates were found to be 0.58, 0.25 and 0.39, respectively. The presence of EMAA filaments of a finite cross-section (i.e., 1.10 mm diameter) in EMAA-0 composite resulted in a substantial increase in laminate thickness (4.49 mm) relative to the baseline composite (1.71 mm). The thermo-forming process

transformed the 1.10 mm-diameter EMAA filaments into relatively thinner films, thus improving the laminate consolidation in EMAA-4. However, despite the improved laminate consolidation, the carbon fibre volume fraction was still lower (0.39) than measured for the baseline composite (0.58). The carbon fibre volume content in composites incorporating EMAA can be increased to match that of the baseline composite by thermo-forming under an increased applied external pressure (e.g., autoclave or hot press) for prolonged periods. The EMAA volume fractions in EMAA-0 and EMAA-4 were determined by analysing the X-ray CT images and found to be 0.14 and 0.20, respectively.

Fig. 3 shows representative X-ray tomographic images of selected sections along the length of the pristine DCB specimens for EMAA-0 and EMAA-4. While porosity was found to be generally low (typically less than 2 vol. %) for all three composites, the inclusion of EMAA seemed to be promoting void formation. The composite porosity was highest in the thermo-formed composites probably due to the presence of cylindrical or film-like EMAA filaments, which would have interfered with the resin flow patterns during the VBRI process via wicking. The EMAA filaments in EMAA-0 maintained their cylindrical geometry as evident from Fig. 3(a). On the other hand, thermo-forming caused EMAA filaments to lose their cylindrical profile forming an interconnected 3D network. Fig. 3(b) reveals the intraply and interply fusion between EMAA filaments embedded in carbon fabric plies following the thermo-forming step.

Figure 3: X-ray CT images of the (a) EMAA-0 and (b) EMAA-4 composites, respectively. The green, red and yellow colours represent the EMAA, carbon fibres and epoxy matrix, respectively.

3.2 Fracture toughness properties

The mode I critical strain energy release rates (G_{Ic}) calculated according to Eqn (1) were plotted against the delamination crack length to generate R -curves for the composites with and without EMAA as shown in Fig. 4. The critical strain energy release rates for all three composites gradually increased with the increase in the delamination crack length reaching quasi-steady-state crack growth resistance for delamination lengths greater than 30 mm. For the baseline composite, the gradual increase in the G_{Ic} values was attributed to carbon fibre bridging. While the steady-state portion of the baseline composite was reasonably stable, the same could not be said of the EMAA-incorporating composites. The discernible instability in delamination crack growth for EMAA-enhanced composites was attributed to the stick/slip crack growth behaviour caused by the non-uniform distribution of EMAA along the delamination crack plane. The resistance to delamination crack initiation for the baseline composite was found to be 0.32 ± 0.03 kJ/m² and in good agreement with values reported for similar systems [26, 27]. The presence of EMAA increased the crack initiation fracture toughness by over 200% for EMAA-0 (1.00 ± 0.06 kJ/m²) and by about 180% for EMAA-4 (0.90 ± 0.14 kJ/m²). Similarly, the steady-state interlaminar fracture toughness for EMAA-incorporating composites improved by at least 240% relative to the baseline laminate.

Figure 4: Representative mode I crack growth resistance R -curves for the investigated composites.

The increase in both the initiation and steady-state crack resistance for EMAA-incorporated composites was attributed to the unique toughening mechanisms invoked by the presence of EMAA along the crack delamination pathway. The X-ray CT image of the delaminated EMAA-0 specimen in Fig. 5(a) revealed crack bifurcation, crack branching, crack deflection around EMAA filaments, crack arrest by the EMAA filaments and debonding of the EMAA filaments from the surrounding epoxy matrix. The interaction of the crack plastic zone with the EMAA filaments, particularly the interfacial debonding from the epoxy matrix, reduces the triaxial stresses operating ahead of the crack tip, thereby effectively enhancing the steady-state fracture toughness. The primary toughening mechanisms in EMAA-4 as revealed by the X-ray CT image (Fig. 5(b)) were crack bifurcation, crack branching and EMAA ligament bridging in the wake of the delamination crack. As already discussed above (see section 3.1), the thermo-forming process resulted in the fusion of EMAA filaments incorporated in adjacent plies, thereby creating a 3D toughening network. The crack bridging traction loads generated by the interconnected EMAA ligaments aligned along the laminate z -direction resisted crack opening under applied through-the-thickness loads, thus effectively slowing down delamination growth. In addition to these unique energy dissipation pathways which were not present in the baseline composite, the intrinsic fracture toughness of EMAA is also superior to that of the epoxy matrix.

Figure 5: X-ray CT images of delaminated (a) EMAA-0 and (b) EMAA-4 composites, respectively.

3.3 Self-repair of the EMAA-incorporated composite laminates

The healing efficiency of composites incorporating EMAA was investigated by re-evaluating the fracture toughness of the repaired composite according to the procedure described in section 2.2. The initiation and steady-state interlaminar fracture toughness of EMAA-enhanced composites in the pristine and healed states are shown in Fig. 6(a) and (b), respectively. A full recovery to the steady-state fracture toughness was achieved from the healing operation for EMAA-0 and EMAA-4 composites. The steady-state fracture toughness values of EMAA-0 and EMAA-4 composites following the healing operation were 6% and 23% greater than the values measured for the pristine composites, respectively.

Figure 6: Effect of healing on the (a) crack initiation and (b) steady-state fracture toughness of the EMAA-incorporated composites.

In both EMAA-0 and EMAA-4 composites, delamination damage repair was enabled by the ability of EMAA to melt and flow into the delamination crack during the healing process. At an elevated temperature (150°C), the resin matrix epoxide groups react with the EMAA acid functional groups forming an abundance of hydroxyl groups. The acid and hydroxyl functional groups then react in the presence of a tertiary amine-catalyst forming EMAA-epoxy covalent bonds as well as small amounts of water. Similarly, the acid groups can react with amines to form amide covalent bonds between the

EMAA and epoxy resin while releasing water. The water molecules produced from both the acid-hydroxyl and acid-amine reactions exist as high-pressure microbubbles within the molten EMAA, thereby enabling a pressure delivery mechanism for EMAA into the delamination cracks [28]. Upon cooling, the EMAA at the crack surfaces solidifies forming strong interfacial bonds to the cured epoxy matrix. Therefore, to achieve effective healing, the EMAA acid functional groups must be present at the crack faces and available to react with the epoxy hydroxyl and amine functional groups. As shown in Fig. 3, thermo-forming resulted in the spread of EMAA at the ply-ply interfaces, which happens to be the delamination pathway.

The greater improvement in the steady-state fracture toughness of EMAA-4 relatively to EMAA-0 following the healing operation may be attributed to the distribution of the EMAA within the laminate structure. In EMAA-0, the thermoplastic filaments are sparsely distributed throughout the composite thereby reducing the probability of acid-hydroxyl and acid-amine reactions which would have otherwise contributed to the recovery in the steady-state fracture toughness. For EMAA-4, the thermoplastic healing agent exists in the form of thin films more evenly spread along the delamination plane thus enabling the formation of a larger number of covalent bonds between the healing agent and the cured epoxy matrix. Further, the fractured crack-bridging EMAA ligaments which were responsible for the increased fracture toughness in pristine EMAA-4 composite, fused during the healing operation resulting in a greater recovery in the steady-state interlaminar fracture toughness for both the EMAA-4 compared to EMAA-0 composite.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the effect of co-braiding self-healing thermoplastic filaments with continuous carbon fibre tows on the interlaminar fracture toughness and delamination repair of FRP composites. The presence of EMAA improved the interlaminar fracture toughness of the carbon-epoxy composite. In EMAA-0, the cylindrical geometric profile of the healing filaments enhanced the initiation and steady-state fracture toughness via toughening mechanisms involving crack deflection around the EMAA filaments, crack arrest by the EMAA filaments, crack bifurcation and branching, and debonding of the EMAA-epoxy interface. Crack-bridging EMAA ligaments and crack branching were the dominant toughening mechanisms in the thermo-formed composite, EMAA-4. EMAA-incorporated composites fully-recovered their pristine-state fracture toughness after the healing.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Quaresimin, K. Schulte, M. Zappalorto and S. Chandrasekaran, Toughening mechanisms in polymer nanocomposites: From experiments to modelling, *Composites Science and Technology*, **123**, 2016, pp. 187-204.
- [2] A. Taloni, M. Vodret, G. Costantini and S. Zapperi, Size effects on the fracture of microscale and nanoscale materials, *Nature Reviews*, **3**, 2018, pp. 211-224.
- [3] H. Saghafi, M. Fotouhi and G. Minak, Improvement of the impact properties of composite laminates by means of nano-modification of the matrix – A review, *Applied Sciences*, **8**, 2018, p. 2406.
- [4] A.Y. Al-Maharma, P. Sendur and N. Al-Huniti, Critical review of the factors dominating the fracture toughness of CNT reinforced polymer composites, *Materials Research Express*, **6**, 2019, p. 012003.
- [5] Z. Ahmadi, Nanostructured epoxy adhesives: A review, *Progress in Organic Coatings*, **135**, 2019, pp. 449-453.
- [6] B.T. Marouf, Y-W. Mai, R. Bagheri and R.A. Pearson, Toughening of epoxy nanocomposites: Nano and hybrid effects, *Polymer Reviews*, **56**, 2016, pp. 70-112.
- [7] I. Gnaba, X. Legrand, P. Wang and D. Soulat, Through-the-thickness reinforcement for composite structures: A review, *Journal of Industrial Textiles*, **49**, 2019, pp. 71-96.
- [8] K.T. Tan, N. Watanabe and Y. Iwahori, Impact damage resistance, response, and mechanisms of laminated composites reinforced by through-thickness stitching, *International Journal of Damage Mechanics*, **21**, 2012, pp. 51-80.

- [9] D.B. Bortoluzzi, G.F. Gomes, D. Hirayama and A.C. Ancelotti Jr, Development of a 3D reinforcement by tufting in carbon fiber/epoxy composites, *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, **100**, 2019, pp. 1593-1605.
- [10] A.P. Mouritz, Review of z-pinned composite laminates, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **38**, 2007, pp. 2383-2397.
- [11] A.R. Ravindran, R.B. Ladani, S. Wu, A.J. Kinloch, C.H. Wang and A.P. Mouritz, Multi-scale toughening of epoxy composites via electric field alignment of carbon nanofibres and short carbon fibres, *Composites Science and Technology*, **167**, 2018, pp. 115-125.
- [12] A.R. Ravindran, R.B. Ladani, C.H. Wang and A.P. Mouritz, Synergistic delamination toughening of composites using multi-scale carbon reinforcements, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **161**, 2019, pp. 18-28.
- [13] A.R. Ravindran, R.B. Ladani, C.H. Wang and A.P. Mouritz, Hierarchical mode I and mode II interlaminar toughening of Z-pinned composites using 1D and 2D carbon nanofillers *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **124**, 2019, p. 105470.
- [14] K.B. Katnam, L.F.M. Da Silva and T.M. Young, Bonded repair of composite aircraft structures: A review of scientific challenges and opportunities, *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, **61**, 2013, pp. 26-42.
- [15] C. Dooley and D. Taylor, Self-healing materials: what can nature teach us? *Fatigue and Fracture of Engineering Materials and Structures*, **40**, 2017, pp. 655-669.
- [16] M.W. Lee, S. Sett, S. An, S.S. Yoon and A.L. Yarin, Self-healing nanotextured vascular-like materials: Mode I crack propagation, *Applied Materials and Interfaces*, **9**, 2017, pp. 27223-27231.
- [17] M.W. Lee, S. An, S.S. Yoon and A.L. Yarin, Advances in self-healing materials based on vascular networks with mechanical self-repair characteristics, *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science*, **252**, 2018, pp. 21-37.
- [18] N.J. Kanu, E. Gupta, U.K. Vates and G.K. Singh, Self-healing composites: A state-of-the-art review, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **121**, 2019, pp. 474-486.
- [19] I.L. Hia, V. Vahedi and P. Pasbakhsh, Self-healing polymer composites: Prospects, challenges, and applications, *Polymer Reviews*, **56**, 2016, pp. 225-261.
- [20] M. Scheiner, T.J. Dickens and O. Okoli, Progress towards self-healing polymers for composite structural applications, *Polymer*, **83**, 2016, pp. 260-282.
- [21] S. Meure, D.Y. Wu and S. Furman, Polyethylene-co-(methacrylic acid) healing agents for mendable epoxy resins, *Acta Materialia*, **57**, 2009, pp. 4312-4320.
- [22] T. Yang, C.H. Wang, J. Zhang, S. He and A.P. Mouritz, Toughening and self-healing of epoxy matrix laminates using mendable polymer stitching, *Composites Science and Technology*, **72**, 2012, pp. 1396-1401.
- [23] T. Yang, J. Zhang, A.P. Mouritz and C.H. Wang, Healing of carbon fibre-epoxy composite T-joints using mendable polymer fibre stitching, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **45**, 2013, pp. 1499-1507.
- [24] K. Pingkarawat, C.H. Wang, R.J. Varley and A.P. Mouritz, Mechanical properties of mendable composites containing self-healing thermoplastic agents, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **65**, 2014, pp. 10-18.
- [25] K. Pingkarawat and A.P. Mouritz, Stitched mendable composites: Balancing healing performance against mechanical performance, *Composites Structures*, **123**, 2015, pp. 54-64.
- [26] K. Pingkarawat, C.H. Wang, R.J. Varley and A.P. Mouritz, Effect of mendable polymer stitch density on the toughening and healing of delamination cracks in carbon-epoxy laminates, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **50**, 2013, pp. 22-30.
- [27] T. Yang, Y. Du, Z.M. Li and C.H. Wang, Mechanical properties of self-healing carbon fiber-epoxy composite stitched with mendable polymer fiber, *Polymer and Polymer Composites*, **22**, 2014, pp. 329-336.
- [28] S. Meure, R.J. Varley, D.Y. Wu, S. Mayo, K. Nairn and S. Furman, Confirmation of the healing mechanism in a mendable EMAA-epoxy resin, *European Polymer Journal*, **48**, 2012, pp. 524-531.